

DRUG ABUSE AND ITS ACADEMIC IMPLICATIONS AMONG STUDENTS AT THREE SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN MUTASA CENTRAL AREA OF MUTASA DISTRICT

Oyedele, V.¹, Chikwature, W.²ⁱ,

Oyedele, O.³, Kadenha, C.¹

^{1,4}Africa University, P.O. Box 1320, Mutare, Zimbabwe

²Mutare Polytechnic, Research Department, P.O. Box 640, Mutare, Zimbabwe

³Namibia University of Science and Technology, Department of Mathematics and Statistics
Windhoek, Namibia

Abstract:

This project explored the occurrence of drug abuse and its academic implications to students at three secondary schools in Mutasa Central area in Mutasa District. The study used the mixed method research design which combines qualitative and quantitative approaches in one study to answer research questions. The study population for this research comprised 48 secondary school teachers, 3 school heads and 150 students. Random sampling was employed to select the sample for classes within each form. Simple random sampling was used to select 8 senior school prefects for focus group discussions. School heads were selected for the study through purposive sampling for interviews. The main findings were that teachers did not teach anything about drug use during lessons as they concentrated on their subject content. They had some experience in dealing with drug problems in the schools. The main reasons why students took drugs was influence of peer pressure and lack of models at home. The most common drugs taken by students were tobacco and beer obtained from friends and road side markets. Schools experienced conflicts between teachers and students and students performed poorly in examinations as a result of drug abuse in schools. The main recommendations were made were that the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education must formalize and support establishment of vibrant guidance and counselling system in schools and school administrators must establish vibrant guidance and counselling departments which effected individual and peer counselling.

¹ Correspondence: email whatmorec@gmail.com

Teachers should incorporate drug education in the teaching-learning of other subjects and schools should invite guest speakers to address students on danger of drug abuse.

Keywords: drug, drug abuse, drug addition, illegal drug, legal drug, substance abuse, strategies, protective factors, risk factors, youth, child, adolescent, puberty, academic implications, students

1. Introduction

Drug abuse by young people, and problems associated with this behaviour have been part of human history for a long time. What is different today is increased availability of a wide variety of substances and the declining age at which experimentation with these substances take place (WHO, 2016). The world over drug abuse has become a major social problem affecting children most of whom are of school going age. WHO cites alcohol as the leading cause of death for males ages 13-19. Kools (2008) cites of youths who have died after drinking huge doses of alcohol. Interestingly, Johnston (2011) observe that some parents often express relief when they discover that their teenagers are “*only drinking*” yet surveys show that this age group is one of the largest alcohol abusers. According to the US National institute on Drugs, about half of all teenagers in the USA have tried an illicit drug before finishing high school. The report adds: Nearly four out of every five students (77%) have consumed alcohol “*more than just a few sips by end of high school*”. In 2004, nearly 19 million Americans ages 12 and older were using illicit drugs - about 8 percent of the population.

According to a United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) Report (2010), some 200 million people, or 5 percent of the world’s population aged 15 - 64 have used drugs at least once in the last 12 months – 15 million more than the previous year’s estimate. Likewise, according to the World Drug Report (2010), the use of illicit drugs in all nations has increased in recent years. The report goes on to note that the increasing availability of a variety of drugs to an ever widening socio-economic spectrum of consumers is disconcerting, although the main problem at the global level continues to be opiates (notably heroine) followed by cocaine. For most of Europe and Asia, opiates accounted for 62 percent of all drug treatment sought in 2008. While 3.3 to 4.1 per cent of the global population admits to consuming drugs, the most worrisome trend for the UNODC Executive Director is the younger and younger ages at which people are becoming addicted. In Pakistan for example, the share of those who started heroin use at 15-20 years of age has doubled to almost 24 percent. A survey in the Czech Republic showed that 37 percent of new drug users were teenagers between 15 and 19

years old. In Egypt, drug use - in particular heroin use - is becoming a serious problem and nearly 6 percent of secondary school students admit to having experimented with drugs.

The World Drug Report by UNODC (2010) reports that there are about 141 million drug abusers globally, including 8 million heroin addicts, 30 million amphetamine users and 13 million cocaine users. The report shows that in the United States and Canada there were 360,000 heroin abusers in 1991, and 600,000 in 2000. In the UK, Ireland, Denmark and Italy, 2 percent of 16 and 17 year-olds had used heroin. Six percent of American young people including students had used cocaine, in the Bahamas 6.4 percent, and 4.5 percent in Kenya. Some 8.3 percent of all young people in the UK and 9 percent in Ireland had used amphetamine drugs (UNODC, 2010).

The National Survey on Drug Use and Health (NSDUH, 2010) revealed that 8.3 percent of the American population roughly 19.5 million people were current users of an illegal drug, while countless more individuals used and abused legal drugs. Moreover almost one half of the US population (46 percent) of 12 years age and older had used an illegal drug at least once at some point in their lives. This is evidence that the country continues to be deeply affected by substance abuse. The most commonly abused drugs were found to be marijuana, cocaine, heroin, inhalants, alcohol and tobacco. The projected economic cost of illicit drug use to US society in 2002 was estimated at \$160.7 billion.

Arguments about drug safety and what drugs should be legal or illegal have existed for centuries. For example, caffeine was once thought to be more dangerous than opium. Three hundred years ago smoking was encouraged because it produced beneficial airs. Today we know that caffeine is a mild drug while opium and tobacco are killers. Hufferman and Vernoy (2009) cited 5000 B.C. as the first recorded use of opium by the Sumerians. Action (2000) observes that around 3500 BC, an ancient scroll describes a brewery for the production of alcohol. Around 3000BC, marijuana is used as folk medicine in central Asia and China.

In 1493, Columbus returns to Europe and introduces smoking tobacco. The Zambezi valley's Tonga people are recorded around 1500 as smoking mbanje using the Tonga pipe (inkolwa). About 1600 AD, the Ottoman Empire introduces death penalty for smoking tobacco while China and Russia also impose strict sanctions on tobacco. Schaefer (2011) actually observe that some substances which have been widely accepted for everyday use when they were first discovered, include cocaine which was used by psychologists, LSD given to soldiers by governments, and also opium for medicinal purposes. In many countries caffeine, nicotine, and alcohol (which are extremely addictive) are being utilized by most individuals in their daily lives, despite the harmful

effects they can have on the body. According to Hufferman and Vernoy (2009) this can create confusion within our society for our youth as to what is or is not acceptable or harmful. For decades, effective prevention and treatment programs have been extremely challenging to create.

On alcohol abuse, the Institute for Social Research at the University of Michigan (2007) points out that by the time learners in the US reach grade 12, approximately 8 in 10 will have consumed alcohol at some time in their lives. Of these, 60 percent will have consumed it to the point of intoxication. Some of the problems associated with youth drinking include violence, suicidal behaviour, and high-risk sexual activity Kools (2008).

In Zimbabwe, drug abuse among school children remains a challenge. According to the Anti-Drug Abuse Association of Zimbabwe (ADAAZ), the major cause of concern is that a significant proportion of these young people eventually get addicted posing a threat to their own health and safety, while creating difficulties for their families and the public at large into difficulties

In Zimbabwe the Education Act of 1987 clearly disallows students from taking alcoholic drinks or be found drunk both within and outside the school premises. Unfortunately these regulations may not be sufficiently enforced as some teachers may be drinking on the job and possibly do not report children who come drunk to school (Financial Gazette 29 January 2015). Beer outlets are prohibited by Zimbabwean law from selling alcoholic beverages and cigarettes to children under the age of 18 but this may not be enforced due to a negative economic situation that has prevailed in the country for the past few years with mushrooming of vendors selling cigarettes and alcohol in undesignated areas.

The research will assess the occurrence of drug abuse and its academic implications among rural students. The research will also unveil other untapped factors that cause drug abuse and its academic implications. A holistic appreciation of all factors that cause drug abuse amongst secondary school children will be enhanced thereby help in addressing the effects among school children.

The case study of drug abuse at School A, School Band Schools C was to be primarily an academic study that was motivated by the desire to get insights on how rural school children possibly abuse substance given the location and character of the three schools. The schools are among the most populous school in the district. They have high catchment area of students than most schools in the district. With a number of bottle stores in the vicinity of the schools, the researcher will appreciate how the students there are coping. The researcher is interested in knowing the rural area with a

view of recommending appropriate and effective social work responses befitting the situation.

Geographically School A is surrounded by two major business centres where beer is the mainstay of those centres namely Nyamunokora, Dzvinyu and Nyaumwe and it is possible school children maybe accessing it there. Nearness to Selbourne Estate may also be a problem since beer drinking is rife in its compounds and children can easily get piece jobs which can enable them to access drugs. School B is close to the popular Watsomba business centre. School C is close to Muchinguri shopping centre where there are many small businesses including bottle stores that sell various types of alcoholic beverages. The study will be used to increase social work knowledge base and improve social work response in the area of juvenile delinquency and drug abuse particularly in schools.

According to the Anti- Drug Abuse Association of Zimbabwe, drug abuse is a general problem in Zimbabwe today especially in areas where there is no adequate supervision i.e. monitoring of students. Social influence and pressure can lead to behaviours like substance abuse, risk taking, and promiscuous sexual activity. Behaviours such as these are detrimental to the health of young people. Drug abuse may be responsible for destruction of property in schools, school failure and broken families. While beer halls and other beer outlets are also prohibited by Zimbabwean law from selling alcoholic beverages and cigarettes to children under the age of 18 this may not be enforced due to a negative economic situation that has prevailed in the country for the past few years forcing the traders to turn a blind eye on children buying alcohol and cigarettes. The issue of illicit brews maybe a problem in rural areas as it is brew in homes without any control measures for the children and students.

Research Questions

1. What are the main causes of drug abuse among children in secondary schools?
2. What are the academic implications of drug abuse among secondary school students?
3. Which are the drugs commonly abused by students in secondary schools?
4. What are the mechanisms available to control drug abuse at school and the surrounding community?
5. How effective are the methods used by schools to address drug abuse?

Materials and Methods

Research Design

Oyedele (2011) define a research design as the plan, structure and strategy on investigation conceived as to obtain answers to research questions. The researcher used the mixed method research design. The design mixes both the quantitative methods and qualitative approach in the same study. The choice of this design was influenced by the nature of the problem, the population to be studied and resources available. It was also found ideal due to its capacity to observe with insight through the use of the questionnaires and interviews with a high degree of precision. The use of multiple methods facilitated the validation of data through cross verification from the wide range of available sources (triangulation).

Population

Population is referred to as the universe. It is a form of conglomeration of all the elements or subjects (Oyedele, 2011). This is the group that the researcher engaged to get information or results of the study. There are 42 secondary schools in Mutasa district and the study focused on three schools in Mutasa central. Focusing on three schools will enable comprehensive analysis and research. The study population for this research comprise secondary school students, teachers and members of the School Development Committee (SDC). A total of 50 students participated at each school. In addition, 16 teachers and 3 SDC members also participated at each of the three schools.

Sample and Sampling Procedure

Sampling is taking any portion of a population or universe as representative of that population or universe (Oyedele, 2011). Level of schooling (forms) was the sampling units for the first stage. McLeod (2015) defines sampling as *“a means by which a selection is made from the basic unit of the study”*. Sampling allows the researcher to select some people to participate in the study.

Random sampling was employed to select the sample for classes within each form. The researchers randomly selected 50 students at each of the three secondary schools (School A, School B and Schools C) to participate in the study through questionnaires. In addition, 16 teachers were selected at each of these schools. Key informants that were sampled for the study include the District Education Officer; Schools heads and three teachers per school. This enabled the researchers to obtain data from all informants at a cheaper cost in terms of time and resources. The school heads were chosen to participate in the study through purposive sampling.

Data Collection Instruments

Questionnaire

A questionnaire is an instrument of measurement and data collection which is used to compile information from people (Oyedele, 2011). It involves the incorporation of peoples' views, opinion, perceptions, habits and behaviours on a certain topic, event or occasion. The questionnaire document usually asks many people the same questions to which the respondents record their answers either in written form or ticking in the boxes provided, (Oyedele, 2011). In this research the following instruments were used:

a. Interviews

An interview is a two person conversation initiated by the interviewer for the specific purpose of obtaining research relevant information, and focus by him on the content specified by research objectives of systematic description, prediction or explanation (Cannel and Kahn, 2010 in Oyedele, 2011). For the purpose of this research personal interviews will be used and these will be semi-structured. Gill and Johnson (2010) define a personal interview as a systematic way of gathering information through asking the same set of questions in a consistent manner to all selected respondents on a face-to-face basis. Interviews are particularly useful for getting a story behind a participant's experiences, beliefs and feelings. Semi-structured interview guides were used with key informants that include the District Education Officer; Schools heads and three teachers per school.

b. Focus Group Discussions

A focus group is a form of qualitative research in which a group of people are asked about their perceptions, opinions, beliefs, and attitudes towards a particular study area. Focus group discussions were employed to the following group of people: (a) "A" Level students both boys and girls, (b) Form Four and Three both boys and girls (c) Form two and one both boys and girls. A total of 10 students participated in each FGD. Given that multiple methods were used for the data gathering process, ideally the methodological triangulation approach was followed as this allowed for the validation of data through cross verification from the wide range of sources. To this end, triangulation of methods facilitated the use of all the data gathering methods at the disposal of the researcher such as documents review, focus group discussions, and questionnaire administration.

Results and Discussion

The qualitative data was analysed by consolidating emerging themes from the FGDs. Data analysis was done using content analysis, a technique widely used in qualitative descriptive research. This involves breaking down transcribed data into thematic smaller units, coding or naming these units according to their content and/or concepts they represent and categorizing or grouping coded material based on shared concepts. Quantitative data was analysed using statistical packages such as the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) and Microsoft Excel. This section presented the results of the research that was carried out on drug abuse and its academic implications among students at three secondary schools in Mutasa central area of Mutasa district with the systematic presentation of research objectives using the data collected from students, teachers and schools development committee members.

Research Objectives

There were 3 research objectives generated for this study and they are presented in a systematic manner as indicated.

A. Research objective 1 which states that “Examine the causes and extent of drug abuse among students at Pafiwa, St Mathias and Zongoro Secondary Schools”.

Responses from the questionnaires, key informant interviews and focus group discussions were used to provide findings to the objective.

Causes of drug abuse

The study established the causes of drug abuse among students at the three secondary schools. Both the teachers and students were asked questions related to the causes of drug abuse by students.

Table 1: Causes of drug abuse

Reason	Yes %	No %
Lack of role models at home	70.8	29.2
Conflict with parents	43.8	56.2
Peer pressure	75	25
A lot of work in school (stress)	25	75
To enhance intellectual ability	6.3	93.7
Break down of family units	66.7	33.3
Excess pocket money	47.9	52.1
Availability of drugs	13	87

Table 1 shows that the highest number of respondents (75%) indicated that students in schools take drugs due to peer pressure. This was seconded by lack of role models at home which had a proportion of 70.8%. The breakdown of family units also accounted for a significant proportion (66.7%). Other causes of drug abuse include excess pocket money and conflict with parents who accounted for 47.9% and 43.8% respectively. The lowest response rate of 6.25% was recorded for the factor that they wanted to enhance intellectual ability. In focused group discussions, it was unearthed that at home, some students smoked and drank beer with their elder brothers. In some cases, they were involved in family rituals in which parents brewed beer. It also some students were drawn into drug abuse due to influence of friends when they met outside the school yard during the lunch hour period or break time. It was further revealed that taking of dagga was said to create in students a very pleasurable sensation which was believed to add to them intellectual potential. These findings could mean that for both home and school factors students abused drugs. NSDUH (2008) highlight that drug abuse is caused by a combination of environmental, biological, and psychological factors. The environmental factors are the most influential include the family, peer association, school performance and social class membership. The world over drug abuse has become a major social problem affecting children most of whom are of school going age.

Student levels involved in drug abuse

Figure 1: Student levels involved in drug abuse

Figure 9 shows that the highest proportion of respondents, 40% indicated that form 4 students were mostly involved in drug abuse. A total of 30% of the respondents reported that the form three students are involved in drug abuse while 10% reported

form six. The lowest response rate of 2 % was reported for form 1 students. In focused group discussions, it was revealed that although drug abuse was done by students at various levels, it was very common among examinable classes and senior classes. The key informants interviewed reported that the examinable classes usually abuse drugs on the pretext that they will be leaving the school. Other attributed abuse of drugs by these forms to the excitement to finishing another level while peer pressure was also cited by both students and teachers. The school heads also confirmed this trend in interviews with the researcher.

Education programmes on drug use in schools

The study also assessed whether teachers teach anything on drug use. This was critical as education programmes in schools increasing knowledge and awareness about effects of drug abuse

Figure 2: Education programmes on drug use in schools

Figure 10 shows that the majority 35 (72.91%) of teachers indicated that they do not teach anything about drug use. Only 13 (27.8%) of the respondents gave positive indication. In interviews with school heads, it was confirmed that teachers focused on their subject content. It was rare that they diverted to talk on drugs unless the material was part of the content. Knowledge on the dangers of drug abuse is critical in reducing uptake of drugs by students. Educational programmes thus not only increase knowledge and awareness about effects of drug abuse, but should also bring changes in values, attitudes and beliefs towards drug abuse. In most educational institutions, teaching-learning processes assume the inter-disciplinary approach in which a teacher delivers particular content to satisfy the demands of a particular syllabus. Such an approach is rigid and may not allow integration of teaching of aspects of drug abuse.

B. Research objective 2 which states that “Identify commonly abused drugs among secondary school children and its academic implications”.

Responses from the questionnaires, key informant interviews and focus group discussions were used to provide findings to the objective.

Commonly abused drugs and effects

The study assessed the most commonly abused drugs by students in secondary schools. Knowledge of the most frequently used drugs by students was regarded as important in recommending possible prevention and intervention measures.

Table 2: Type of drugs usually taken by students

Drug	Percentage
Beer	85.4
Spirits	43.8
Mbanje	31.3
Cough syrup	89.6
Glue	58.3
Tobacco	80.0

Table 2 shows that the highest number of respondents (89.58%) indicated that students used cough syrup. Beer was also one of the most commonly used drugs by students constituting a proportion of 85.4%. A significant proportion 80% of the respondents also indicated that students abuse tobacco cigarettes. The lowest response rate was 31.3% recorded for mbanje (dagga). In the focused group discussions, participants indicated that the most common drugs consumed by students include tobacco, dagga, opaque beer and spirits. This was also confirmed by school administrators in interviews with researcher. Beer is easily abused by students because it is easily available in the communities where home brewed beer is usually available for free. Cough syrup was also observed to be easily abused by students because it is difficult to assess whether the syrup is administered for cough or taken in excess to get drunk.

Sources of drugs

Figure 3: Sources of drugs

Figure 11 shows that the majority (52.8%) of respondents indicated that students get drugs from friends. The second highest source of drugs was that registered a response rate of 29.16% was road side markets. The other sources of drugs by students reported include the local shops (8.33%) and family members (6.25%). The lowest response rate of 4.16% was recorded on the perception that students got drugs from elder members of the community. Participants in focused group discussions explained that students got drugs mainly from their colleagues who in most cases obtained the materials from roadside markets run by some dubious community members. Within the immediate vicinity of the schools certain parents depended on students and supplied beer, spirits, tobacco and dagga. The discussions also exposed the unprofessional behaviour of some teachers who shared liquor with students and smoked with them at their houses. These findings imply that students got drugs from sources within the school and the community. It is unbelievable that in some sections of the community, some individuals connive with the youth and avail the substances.

Table 3: Preferred place for taking drugs

Place	Percentage
In the field	64.6
In the classroom	4.2
In the toilet	87.5
In the thickets	89.6
Away from school	93.8

Table 3 shows that the highest number of respondents, (93.8%) indicated that students in schools took drugs while away from school. A significant proportion 89.6% and 87.5% of the respondents indicated that students prefer to take drugs in the thickets and toilet respectively. A total of 64.6% reported that students take drugs in the fields while only 4.2% reported that students take drugs in the classroom. Focused group discussions revealed that drug abuse took in secluded places when the students could not be seen by teachers and other respected members of the community. The fact that students take drugs in secluded places shows that they are aware of the illegality of taking drugs. Key informants interviewed reported that they type of drugs taken in the classrooms are those that do not produce unpleasant smell such as cough syrup. It was acknowledged that students were aware that their behaviour was immoral. In interviews, school heads said that within the school environment, the toilet was a suspected location where smoking took place because students took advantage of the fact that this is a private place which if a teacher entered to monitor student activity there, it could be regarded an abuse of human rights. These findings could mean that students abused drugs in private places where they could not be easily noticed. All these responses suggest that drugs are taken in secretive areas where abusers may never be found by school authorities and even parents. The choice of secret places for drug abuse could be necessitated by strict school rules where discovery would lead to expel from school. In addition, the illegal status of most drugs of abuse in the country could explain why drugs are taken in in hidden places.

Problems faced by schools due to drug abuse

The study established from teachers whether their schools have experienced by problems due to drug abuse by students. This was important to establish the academic implications of drug abuse.

Figure 4: Problems faced by schools to drug abuse

Figure 12 shows that the highest number of respondents, 41(85.41%) indicated that schools experienced problems due to drug abuse among students. Only 7(14.58%) made a negative indication on the perception. Key informant interviews in school heads indicated that the effects of drug abuse was not only restricted to meeting the disciplinary measures by school authorities. Other students not using drugs suffered psychologically and this was apparent from the FGDs.

Table 4: Problems experienced by schools as a result of drug abuse by students

Problem	Frequency	Percentage
Fighting amongst students	33	68.8
Sneaking	29	60.4
Stealing	21	43.8
Strikes	13	27.1
Conflicts between teachers and students	40	83.3
Poor performance in examinations	42	87.5

Table 4 shows that problems experienced by schools as a result of drug abuse among students were multiple. The respondents to this issue were mainly teachers. The highest number of respondents, 42 (87.5%) indicated that as a result of drug abuse among students schools experienced the problem of poor performance of students in examinations. This response rate of 40 (83.33%) was recorded for the perception that there were conflicts between teachers and students. The other effects of drug abuse included fighting among students (68.8%), sneaking (60.4%) and stealing (43.8%). The lowest response rate was 13 (27.08%) recorded for strikes. In interviews, school heads said that drug abuse has been the chief source of disciplinary problems in schools. They went on to say that as long as a student got involved in drug use, he or she became uncontrollable be it in class or else in the school. One school head said:

“Lady teachers often extreme challenges when teaching classes Student to be involved in drug taking. In one case, a student under the influence of drugs began to propose love to a young student teacher who was on teaching practice.”

These findings that imply that student abuse of drugs caused problems in schools and impeded effective the teaching – learning exercise. Educationists say that unless learners show internal discipline, it is difficult to make progress in their education.

Table 5: Effects of drug abuse on students

Perception	Frequency	Percentage
They do not concentrate in class	43	89.6
The steal from others	25	52.1
They are always punished	32	66.7
They break school rules	46	95.8
They are not co-operative	47	97.9
They are usually absent	31	64.6

Table 5 shows that drug abuse affected students who engage in the vice in a variety of ways. The highest number of respondents, 47 (97.91%) indicated that students ceased to be co-operative. The other effects of drug abuse reported included lack of concentration in class (89.6%), breaking schools rules (95.8%) and absent from school (64.6%). The lowest response rate was 25 (52.08%) recorded for the view that students stole from their colleagues. This trend was confirmed in focused group discussions. Participants said that students who abused drugs lost direction in their life as students. It was revealed that in the majority of cases they showed confusion and lost concentration in their school work. School administrators concurred with this perception and said that one suspected factor that contributed to low student performance and low school pass rate was drug use which caused unruly behaviour among students. Teachers have less time to deliver teaching and have difficulties in effectively managing classroom discipline.

Figure 5: Teachers' experiences in dealing with drug abuse

Figure 13 shows that the highest number of respondents, 39 (81.25%) indicated that teachers have had some experience in dealing with drug problems in the schools. Only

9 (18.75%) gave negative indication. In interviews with school heads, it was revealed that there were several cases when teachers discovered pupils abusing drugs in bushes near the school. In other cases girl students were caught drunk and had to take corrective measures. These findings suggest that teachers have had any experience in dealing with drug problems in the school. Teachers always interacted with students inside and outside the classroom during which they noticed how students took drugs and their effects on their behaviour. Joint effort from the home and school was needed to curb such behaviour.

C. Research objective 3 which states that “Identify and evaluate strategies used in secondary schools to address drug abuse”.

Responses from the questionnaires, key informant interviews and focus group discussions were used to provide findings to the objective.

Measures used to address drug abuse in secondary schools

The study also assessed measures used to address drug abuse in schools. This was important in establishing a holistic approach to ending child abuse in schools.

Table 6: Measures taken to fight drug related problems in schools

Measure	Frequency	Percentage
Expulsion,	3	6.3
Suspension	31	64.6
Guidance and counselling	5	10.4
Ask parents to come to school	43	89.6
Heavy punishment	29	60.4

Table 6 shows that drug abuse affected students who engage in the vice in a variety of ways. The highest number of respondents, 43 (89.6%) indicated that students were ask to bring parents to come to school to look into the issue. This response rate was seconded by 31 (64.58%) which was recorded for suspension. The other measure used in schools in heavy punishment (60.4%) and lowest response rate was 3 (6.3%) recorded for expulsion. In interviews, school Heads indicated that they took disciplinary measured to deal with culprits. They said that they suspended the student for fourteen days after which a hearing would be held in the presence of the guardians or parents. Thereafter, severe punishment would be administered to the culprit. These findings could be an indication that schools tried to deal with cases of drug abuse in a severe way. It has been observed that schools have applied several unorthodox means to deal

with the challenge of drug abuse. The level of effectiveness was low because the strategies did not transform the attitudes of the culprits and behavioural change.

Figure 6: People involved in drug education in schools

Figure 14 shows that the highest number of respondents, 24 (50%) indicated that people involved in drug education at schools were school administrators. The other people involved in drug education included school counsellors (22.92%), class teachers (16.66%) and SDC (6.25%). The lowest response rate of 2 (4.16%) was recorded for the view that it was it was teachers in all subjects. In focused group discussions, participants seemed unaware of any drug education programme in the school. Some participants however argued that the school head sometimes addressed them on issues related with drug abuse. This implies that school administrators exposed students to some information on dangers of drug abuse. The counsellors act as shepherds who play a vital role of pastoral care and counselling to address drug abuse among students.

Table 7: Methods of eradicating drug abuse in schools

Method	Frequency	Percentage
Guidance and counselling	47	97.9
Peer counselling	48	100
Inco-operate drug education to other subjects	39	81.3
Strict school regulations	37	77.8
Invite guest speakers on danger of drug abuse	45	93.8

Table 7 shows that problems experienced by schools as a result of drug abuse among students were multiple. The highest number of respondents, 48 (100%) indicated that schools should do peer counselling. This response rate was seconded by 97 (97.9%) which was recorded for guidance and counselling. The lowest response rate of 37

(77.08%) was recorded for the view that schools should apply strict school regulations. In interviews, school heads agreed that there was need to win students who abused drugs which ruled out inflicting pain on the culprits. They stressed that it was imperative to transform attitudes of the drug abusers through peer counselling and effect guidance and counselling then monitor the situation. It was also revealed that integration of drug education in subject lessons and engaging resource persons would serve the same purpose. These findings suggest that the suggested ways of eradicating drug abuse in schools would help to improve the situation. Bezuidenhout (2008).

Counselling involves the development of help, understanding and support to someone who is perplexed. A warm climate is created so that the client feels accepted and is able to open up and reveal his or her circumstances. He or she gains an insight on how to help himself or herself drawing available resources. In other words counselling is a relationship that is created between the counsellor and counselee and stresses on self-help which will greatly benefit victims of drug abuse.

Table 8: Problems that school authorities encounter in dealing with drug abuse

Perception	Frequency	Percentage
Parents do not support the administration	40	83.3
Some teachers provide drugs to students	34	70.8
Some teachers take drugs	29	60.4
The teachers do not discourage drug taking	27	56.3
Lack of adequate knowledge on drug use	36	75.0
Time schedules are not flexible	28	58.3

The highest number of respondents, 40 (83.3%) indicated that the problem that school authorities encountered in dealing with drug abuse in schools was that parents did not support the school administration. The lowest response rate was 28 (58.3%) recorded for the view that there was lack of adequate knowledge on drug use students. In interviews, school administrators indicated that dealing with students required a combined effort between the school administrators, teachers and parents. This was lacked in most cases students exploited this weakness. In focused group discussions, participants said that some teacher sent students to buy beer and cigarettes. The findings suggest that school authorities encountered problems in dealing with drug abuse in schools. There is a high level of indiscipline in schools and teachers have problems have difficulties in effectively managing classroom.

Conclusions

The study showed that the major causes of drug by students are peer pressure, lack of role models at home. Other causes of drug abuse include excess pocket money and conflict with parents. It was unearthed that at home, some students smoked and drank beer with their elder brothers. The school levels most involved in drug abuse are the form 4 students. The examinable classes usually abuse drugs on the pretext that they will be leaving the school. The commonly abused drugs included cough syrup, beer and tobacco cigarettes. Beer is easily abused by students because it is easily available in the communities where home brewed beer is usually available for free. The major sources of drugs for students included friends and road side markets. Within the immediate vicinity of the schools some parents depended on students and supplied beer, spirits, tobacco and dagga.

The major problems experienced by schools as a result of drug abuse among students include poor performance of students in examinations and conflicts between teachers and students. Students who abuse drugs ceased to be co-operative. The other effects of drug abuse reported included lack of concentration in class, breaking schools rules and absent from school. Students who abused drugs lost direction in their life as students. Measures used by schools to address drug abuse include asking students to bring parents to come to school to look into the issue and suspension. The other measure used in schools in heavy punishment and expulsion. People involved in drug education at schools were school administrators. The other people involved in drug education included school counsellors and class teachers. Methods of eradicating drug abuse in schools include peer counselling, guidance and counselling. It was also revealed that integration of drug education in subject lessons and engaging resource persons would serve the same purpose. The problems that school authorities encountered in dealing with drug abuse in schools included failure of parents to support school administration, participation of some teachers in providing drugs to students and lack of adequate knowledge on drug use.

Implications

There is need for close collaboration between schools and the community in addressing drug abuse. Parents and family members thus should play an effective role in reducing drug abuse among students. In this regard, regular meetings between schools and parents should be encouraged and this enables both the school administration and parents to share ideas on methods to address drug abuse in schools. There is also need

for effective policy with regards how schools should develop strategies to address drug abuse among students.

Recommendations

Following the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations were made. The Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education must formalise and support establishment of a vibrant guidance and counselling system in schools. These should be supported by school administrators through establishing vibrant guidance and counselling departments. The guidance and counselling departments must organise peer counselling in schools with school administrators applying strict school regulations in conjunction with peer counselling and guidance and counselling to reduce drug abuse among students

Teachers should incorporate drug education in the teaching-learning of other subjects. Teacher's` skills development must be central element in programmes addressing drug abuse. To ensure sustainability of the programme, there is need to ensure availability of continued staff training, provision of programme materials, and adequate time for counselling and space for all involved. School guidance and counselling should invite guest speakers to address students on danger of drug abuse. The school educational programmes must not only increase knowledge and awareness about effects of drug abuse, but should also aim at changing values, attitudes and beliefs leading to abuse of drugs. Educational programs on drug abuse among students should therefore be holistic and address both the risk and protective factors.

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